

Refining genome annotations with Apollo

Wednesday 17 November 2021

3-6 pm AEDT/ 2-5pm AEST/ 2:30-5:30pm ACDT/ 12-3pm
AWST

Trainers:

Anthony Bretaudeau, French National Institute for Agriculture, Food, and Environment

Helena Rasche, Erasmus Medical Center, The Netherlands

Dr Sarah Williams, QCIF Bioinformatics

Dr Tiffanie Nelson, Australian BioCommons

Host: Dr Melissa Burke, Australian BioCommons

*Timings are approximate and subject to change. [Check the start time in your location here](#)

Time	Length (mins)	Topic	Who
3:00 pm AEDT 2:00 pm AEST 2:30 pm ACDT 12:00 pm AWST 5:00 am CET	10	Welcome and housekeeping	Melissa
3:10 pm AEDT 2:10 pm AEST 2:40 pm ACDT 12:10 pm AWST 5:10 am CET	5	Introduction to the workshop and the Australian Apollo Service	Tiff
3:15 pm AEDT 2:15 pm AEST 2:45 pm ACDT 12:15 pm AWST 5:15 am CET	5	Overview of the annotation process the <i>E.coli</i> data set	Tiff
3:20 pm AEDT 2:20 pm AEST 2:50pm ACDT 12:20 pm AWST 5:20 am CET	15	Getting started in Apollo	Tiff
3:35 pm AEDT 2:35 pm AEST	15	Hands on	All

3:05pm ACDT 12:35 pm AWST 5:35 am CET		Logging in and getting data into Apollo	
3:50 pm AEDT 2:50 pm AEST 3:20 pm ACDT 12:50 pm AWST 5:50 am CET	5	Evidence tracks	Helena
3:55 pm AEDT 2:55 pm AEST 3:25 pm ACDT 12:55 pm AWST 5:55 am CET	10	Adding new genes	Helena
4:05 pm AEDT 3:05 pm AEST 3:35 pm ACDT 1:05 pm AWST 6:05 am CET	15	Breakout Evidence tracks and adding new genes	
4:20 pm AEDT 3:20 pm AEST 3:50 pm ACDT 1:20 pm AWST 6:20 am CET	5	Editing a gene structure Viewing and reverting changes	Helena
4:25 pm AEDT 3:25 pm AEST 3:55 pm ACDT 1:25 pm AWST 6:25 am CET	5	Breakout room Editing gene structure and viewing and reverting changes	
4:30 pm AEDT 3:30 pm AEST 4:00 pm ACDT 1:30 pm AWST 6:30 am CET	10	Break	
4:40 pm AEDT 3:40 pm AEST 4:10 pm ACDT 1:40 pm AWST 6:40 am CET	10	Adding more functional annotation	Anthony
4:50 pm AEDT 3:50 pm AEST 4:20 pm ACDT 1:50 pm AWST 6:50 am CET	5	Comparing with the official annotation	Anthony
4:55 pm AEDT 3:55 pm AEST 4:25 pm ACDT 1:55 pm AWST 6:55 am CET	20	Breakout room Adding more functional annotation & Comparing with Official Gene Sets	

5:15 pm AEDT 4:15 pm AEST 4:45 pm ACDT 2:15 pm AWST 7:15 am CET	5	Sequence alterations	Anthony
5:20 pm AEDT 4:20 pm AEST 4:50 pm ACDT 2:20 pm AWST 7:20 am CET	10	Breakout room Sequence alterations	
5:30 pm AEDT 4:30 pm AEST 5:00 pm ACDT 2:30 pm AWST 7:30 am CET	5	Exporting annotation	Sarah
5:35 pm AEDT 4:35 pm AEST 5:05 pm ACDT 2:35 pm AWST 7:35 am CET	10	Collaborating with other annotators	Sarah
5:45 pm AEDT 4:45 pm AEST 5:15 pm ACDT 2:45 pm AWST 7:45 am CET	10	Getting access to the Australian Apollo Service Summary and Q&A	Tiff
5:55 pm AEDT 4:55 pm AEST 5:25 pm ACDT 2:55 pm AWST 7:55 am CET	5	Wrap up and feedback	Melissa
6:00 pm AEDT 5:00 pm AEST 5:30 pm ACDT 3:00 pm AWST 8:00 am CET		End of workshop	

Acknowledgements:

This workshop is presented by the [Australian BioCommons](#) and [Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation \(QCIF\)](#).

The [Australian Apollo Service](#) is operated by QCIF and underpinned by computational resources provided by the Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre and receives NCRIS funding through Bioplatforms Australia and the Australian Research Data Commons as well as Queensland Government RICF funding.

**BIOPLATFORMS
AUSTRALIA**

Australian Research Data Commons

The training materials presented in this workshop were developed by Anthony Bretaudeau, Helena Rasche, Nathan Dunn, Mateo Boudet for the Galaxy Training Network.

Helena and Anthony are part of the [Gallantries project](#) which is supported by Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union.

With the support of the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union